

Making Sense of Our Experiences of Solitude and Loneliness

Sebastian Vazhapilly, SJ
Papal Seminary, Pune 411014

In the recent lock-down because of Corona virus epidemic, large numbers of people in most part of the world were forced to confine themselves to their homes. Going by the evidences in the social media, this confinement was not all easy for many people, to say the least. In part, this involuntary isolation caused considerable distress because we are not used to such seclusion. This extraordinary health crisis triggered large number of reflections not only about the virus and preventive measures, but also about the meaning of life and death. However, this crisis situation and the ensuing confinement also produced considerable amount of humour. One particular form of humour focused on the funny side of the forced isolation. Several people posted videos of how this forced confinement is affecting them in creative and humorous manner. For example, as they reach the limits of boredom, some start counting the staircase steps, chairs, tables, electric switches, bulbs, and tube lights in the house. Others start calculating the number of hair in the toothbrush, counting the teeth in the comb, and measuring the time takes for the fan to stop completely.

Humour apart, there is a grain of truth that it is not easy to be alone for a long period of time. One of the reasons for this is rooted in our social nature. Bible contains profound insights into our social nature. We find such insights right in the first

chapter of Genesis which describes the story of creation. After various acts of creation, we are told that 'It was good.' It is repeated at least 7 times. Perhaps the authors of Genesis want to communicate the basic goodness of creation. In the Second chapter God creates Adam, the first man. Then in verse 18 we read: "Then the Lord God said: 'It is not good that the man should be alone.'" The very first thing described as being 'not good' is being 'alone.' He creates a companion, Eve or woman. This is a beautiful way of describing our relatedness and our social nature.

Both solitude and loneliness are related to our social nature. Though there is a tendency to confuse solitude and loneliness, we need to note that our experiences of solitude and loneliness tend to be different.

Both solitude and loneliness are related to our social nature. Though there is a tendency to confuse solitude and loneliness, we need to note that our experiences of solitude and loneliness tend to be different. In this short article, I would like to focus on the differences between solitude and loneliness and the dynamics and forms of loneliness.

Solitude and Loneliness

There are differences between our experience of loneliness and solitude. And it is important to note this difference. Loneliness is not the same thing as being alone. We can be alone, still not feel lonely. So a sense of solitude is not the same as loneliness. In fact, a lack of solitude can bring us a sense of loneliness. We all need solitude at least sometimes. Going by the New Testament data, it would appear that Jesus did embrace solitude. For example, in Mt 14: 23 we read: "After he dismissed the crowds, Jesus went up the mountain by himself to pray. When evening came, he was there alone."

15

In our solitude we meet ourselves. It is here that we meet our true selves. And for many, it can be an experience a little unsettling. But this meeting our true selves at a depth level is also the condition for our growth and maturity. We all need a little 'time out' and a quiet time and space for ourselves. It is time to discover ourselves, to discover our innermost self. It is also a space to grow as mature persons. This is a temporary withdrawal which has nothing to do with how you get along with others. You are not afraid of it; you are not lost in it. When you are in solitude, you are alone. In solitude I am by myself, but I am not lonely.

When we are unable to relate, when we are not able to belong, when we are not accepted, when we are not loved and when we are unable to love, we feel within us a sense of being 'disconnected.' Loneliness is basically our experience of being disconnected.

In solitude, we do not experience a sense of pain or loss of relationships as we do in loneliness. Solitude is a voluntary withdrawal which is temporary. Moreover, unlike loneliness, solitude is the effect of the choice that we make. We do not have many choices regarding the factors contributing to loneliness.

But the lonely ones may attend so many parties, they may get phone calls often, and they may be very popular. And they still feel lonely. We can be surrounded by people, and still be lonely. One can have big social circles, and still can be very lonely. Another may not have big social circles, and yet may not experience loneliness. Often it could be the case that lonely people tend to run around hectically in their effort to mask a deep sense of loneliness.

16

Dynamics and Forms of Loneliness

Loneliness is different from solitude. One of the ways to understand the experience of loneliness is by looking at it as an experience of 'disconnect.' We can ask: what does this disconnect mean? What does this experience of disconnect consists of?

All of us have certain basic human needs such as our need to love and to be loved, to relate to others, to belong to groups, institutions, religion or to other people, to accept others and to be accepted by others. Thus, when we are able to relate in a meaningful way, when we are able to belong to other, to traditions and institutions, when we are accepted by others and when we accept others in a meaningful way, when we are able to love in a meaningful way, we experience some of 'connection.' When these things are present, we feel that we are somehow 'connected.'

On the other hand, when we are unable to relate, when we are not able to belong, when we are not accepted, when we are not loved and when we are unable to love, we feel within us a sense of being 'disconnected.' Loneliness is basically our experience of being disconnected. Loneliness is the feeling of not really mattering to anyone, of not being significant, of being isolated, of being alone in the sense of not being important to anyone.¹

Loneliness is not only difficult, but it is also a condition difficult to explain. The main reason for this could be that there are various types of loneliness or sources of loneliness. We shall mention six types of loneliness here, though by no means this list is exhaustive.

Separation from Other People: There is one form of loneliness which results from the separation from other people. There can be many reasons for such separation. It could be separation from people and groups with whom we have worked closely. They had meant much to us. Now they are not with us. Separation could be in the form of death of loved ones. Sometimes, the separation can

17

result of deep hurt or abuse. They find it difficult to trust others because they have been taken advantage of or exploited. Or it could be rejection of love. Or it could be our inability to love others in a meaningful way. It could also result from non-acceptance from others.

Alienation from One's Own Self: One of the devastating forms of loneliness is the alienation from one's own self. It is also very destructive because there is a loss of self and a loss of meaning. There can be several reasons for this form of self-alienation. It could be because a deep sense of guilt in our life. The loneliness of guilt can be at times terrible. We have done some wrong and we feel guilty about it. Guilt is ultimately the anger directed against oneself. Often many of us feel trapped in guilt, eating away our peace and a sense of well-being. We are alone with the burden of our guilt. Sometimes people feel self-alienated because of a combination of reasons: it could be because of a lack of belongingness, a sense of failure in life or it could be a sense of rejection. Some of these feelings can be diffused and often vague but leading gradually to a sense of loneliness.

18

Loneliness resulting from our Work: Sometimes, those who pioneer certain type of work also may feel a sense of loneliness. Often, this can result from a sense of not being understood; it can come from a lack of support that one might feel in starting something new. Some letters of pioneering missionaries like Francis Xavier and Robert de Nobili reflect this form of loneliness. At other times, sheer volume of work involved, and a lack of being alone in our work also can result in loneliness.

Existential Loneliness: In spite of love and communion, there remains the realization that ultimately in some way, I am alone. I may have the support and help but still I face my life alone. To be lonely is part of being human. That is the existential loneliness. In this sense, some degree of loneliness cannot be avoided. Even married people feel lonely at times; man and woman remain alone even in the most intimate union.² We can try to run away from it, go to different parties or we can even pretend that it does not exist. But our existential loneliness remains as part of our life.

Cultural Alienation/Loneliness: A person may live in a culture different from one's own. One may speak the language of that particular culture but still feel alienated. This can be a common experience of religious who work in a different culture. We are neither rooted in our own culture, nor in the adopted culture. Often we do not feel quite connected in the adopted culture. Many of us feel a sense of cultural displacement. As a result many of us seek to connect with our own ethnic and cultural groups. Here, we need to note that this form of alienation results from a lack of belonging to cultural tradition.

Loneliness of the Elderly: For many elderly people, loneliness can come in the form of shrinking circle of friends. It is also the realization that we are not in a position to expand that circle again. We see people of our age group slowly disappearing from existence. Suddenly we see those who are close to us are not with us anymore. Sometimes many old people feel that they are not wanted. All these can add up to the experience of loneliness experienced by the elderly people. Some of us may grow old gracefully; others may not be so lucky.

So, there are various sources of loneliness and forms of loneliness. And the experience of loneliness differs from person to person.

19

Much of it depends on our personality traits and up-brining and our mental make-up.

Conclusion

As with our differing experiences of loneliness, our capacity to cope with loneliness also differs. Some of us are better equipped with it while others may not be able to cope with it. All the same, it is never too late to learn something about loneliness and in that process, we can also learn something about ourselves. Whatever the case, prolonged loneliness can have its effects on our lives and on our work. Loneliness often is part of being human and there may not be simple solutions to deal with it. Distractions can diminish the pain of loneliness but it does not meet the problem at its root. We can ignore loneliness – but it will come back with a vengeance. So, we need to face our experience of loneliness and try to deal with it as best as we can. Often, our loneliness can be an invitation and challenge. It can be a valuable opportunity for our growth. Some problems in our lives cannot be resolved fully and completely. Loneliness is one of them. So, we learn to live with them, to make best out of them. It can be an opportunity to learn more about ourselves and our shadows.

20

¹ Robert Lauder, *Loneliness is for Loving* (Indiana: Ave Maria Press, 1978) p. 10.

² Paul Tillich, *The Boundaries of Our Being* (London & Glasgow: Collins, 1973) p. 16.